

THERMOELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF Ni/TiO_{2-x} COMPOSITESY. Lu^{1*}, K. Sagara¹, Y. Matsuda¹, L. Hao¹, H. Yoshida², J.X. Chen³

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* Corresponding author (luyun@faculty.chiba-u.jp)**Keywords:** Ni/TiO_{2-x} composite, thermoelectric property, carrier density, carrier mobility**1 Introduction**

Generally, the performance of a thermoelectric material is evaluated by the figure of merit, Z or the dimensionless figure of merit, ZT as follows.

$$ZT = S^2 \rho^{-1} \kappa^{-1} T \quad (1)$$

where S is the Seebeck coefficient, ρ is the electrical resistivity, κ is the thermal conductivity and T is absolute temperature. For convenience, the power factor P is always used to evaluate the performance of thermoelectrics with the following formula.

$$P = S^2 \rho^{-1} \quad (2)$$

Therefore, to improve the performance of thermoelectrics, the Seebeck coefficient S should be increased, the electrical resistivity ρ and the thermal conductivity κ should be decreased. In recent years, the composite methods have attracted much attention in enhancing the thermoelectric performance. The improvement of thermoelectric performance by adding metal powder, such as Au and Ag to oxide thermoelectrics, has been tried [1-5]. In these works, the electrical resistivity was largely decreased by adding metal powder. Indeed, the Seebeck coefficient had an increase in some works [1,2,4]. Consequently, it led to enhancement of the power factor. In our previous work, it was revealed that the power factor gave the biggest value at the amount of adding 12%Cu into Cu/TiO_{2-x} composite, at which the transition from semiconductor to metal appeared [6]. Besides, the sandwich-structured composite has been used thermoelectrics to enhance the power factor [7-10]. In those works, it was revealed that the power factor can be enhanced by the sandwich-structured composites with series structure of metal/semiconductor/metal. However, composite method is always accompanied with some negative effects including the increase of thermal conductivity. It seems necessary to investigate the

composite effect and their influence of the added metals on thermoelectric properties. The metals used as the additives in composite thermoelectrics such as Cu, Ag and Au have very low electrical resistivity, while they have low thermoelectric performance due to small Seebeck coefficients and great thermal conductivities as listed in Table 1. However, Ni has high thermoelectric performance as its relative great Seebeck coefficient and small thermal conductivity.

Table 1 Thermoelectric properties of the added metals at room temperature (298 K).

Property	Cu ^{*1}	Ni ^{*1}	Ag	Au
ρ ($\mu\Omega\text{m}$)	0.0171	0.0720	0.0021 ^{*2}	0.0032 ^{*2}
S (μVK^{-1})	1.9	-15	1.38 ^{*3}	1.74 ^{*3}
κ ($\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$)	401	91	428 ^{*2}	319 ^{*2}
P ($\text{mWm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-2}$)	0.21	3.13	1.09	1.12
$ZT \times 10^{-3}$	0.157	10.2	0.756	1.042

*1 Reference [7], *2 Reference [11] and *3 Reference [12]

In this work, Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites added Ni powder to nonstoichiometric titanium dioxide TiO_{2-x} was fabricated by spark plasma sintering (SPS). The compositions and crystal forms of the composites were examined. The thermoelectric properties of the composites were also investigated. The carrier density and mobility of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites were examined by hall effect measurement.

2 Experimental**2.1 Fabrication and characterization of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites**

Rutile TiO₂ powder of purity 99.0% and average diameter 0.3 μm was used as the matrix. Ni powder of purity 99.9% and average diameter 10 μm was

used as the metal additive. Volume fraction of Ni powder added to the composites varied from 0% to 45%. The source materials, tungsten carbide balls and acetone were placed in a bowl made of alumina. Blending was performed using a planetary ball-mill (Pulverisette 5/4, Fritsch) with a rotation speed of 300 rpm for 2 h, and then the mixed powder was dried. After that, the mixed powder was also blended in the same conditions for 2 h. After blending, the mixed powder were charged into a graphite die (diameter 40 mm) as dense as possible. Then, the die was fixed in the SPS system (SPS-1030, Sumitomo). The compacts with dimensions of ϕ 40 mm \times 1.5 mm were fabricated by SPS at 1273 K and holding for 5 min under a pressure of 27.3 MPa. After the fabrication, bulk samples with dimensions of 40 mm \times 5 mm \times 1.5 mm were cut from the compacts for the measurements. The compositions and crystal forms of the composites were examined by XRD. The microstructures of the composites were observed by SEM.

2.2 Measurement of thermoelectric properties

The plate samples of the Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites with dimensions of 40 mm \times 5 mm \times 1.5 mm were used for thermoelectric property measurements. To obtain a uniform temperature gradient along the length direction of the plate sample for the Seebeck coefficient measurement, a tubular electrical furnace with two controllable heaters was used. The measurements were carried out from approximately 323 K up to 973 K in air. The Seebeck coefficient was measured by the static method. The plate sample was heated, and held at the measurement temperatures. Then, it was given a temperature difference of ± 6 K along the length of the sample, in other words, a temperature gradient between the two sides of the sample. The negative temperature difference implies a reverse temperature gradient. The Seebeck coefficient was calculated from the $\Delta T - \Delta V$ curve. The electrical resistivity at the elevated temperatures was measured by the four-probe method when the temperature difference was 0 K.

2.3 Hall effect measurement

Hall effect measurement was carried out by van der Pauw method in the magnetic field density of 1 T at room temperature. Square samples with dimensions

of 10 mm \times 10 mm \times 0.5 mm were used. The four electrodes were fixed on the four corners. The carrier density and mobility of the Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites were calculated by the obtained hall coefficient.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Fabricated Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites

From the SEM micrographs of the Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites shown in Fig.1, it is found that the Ni particles were lengthened and distributed in the matrix TiO_{2-x} uniformly. The diffraction peaks of Ni and TiO_{2-x} were detected from the XRD patterns of the composites shown in Fig.2. As the added volume fraction of Ni powder increased, the peaks of Ni became intenser and those of TiO_{2-x} got lower. From the above results, it can be confirmed that the composites consisted of Ni and TiO_{2-x} without any reactions in the fabrication processes.

3.2 Thermoelectric properties of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites

When the volume fraction of Ni powder was no more than 22%, the electrical resistivities of the composites showed a decrease tendency with the increase of measurement temperature, as shown in Fig.3. It is a typical semiconductor behavior. However, the electrical resistivities turned to increase with the increase of measurement temperature when the volume fraction of Ni powder was more than 22%. Thus, it is a typical metallic behavior. The electrical behavior transition from semiconductor to metal for the Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites can be controlled by adjusting the added volume fraction of Ni powder. In our previous work, the electrical behavior transition from semiconductor to metal appeared in the Cu/TiO_{2-x} composites [6], while the volume fraction of the transition was 12%Cu, which is lower than that (22%Ni) of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites. From the relationship between the electrical resistivity and the Ni volume fraction shown in Fig.4, it is clearly found that the point of the transition is 22%.

The Seebeck coefficient showed minus values, which mean that Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites are n-type semiconductor. For convenience, The Seebeck coefficient was given by the absolute values as shown in Fig.5 and Fig.6. The Seebeck coefficient decreased as the Ni volume fraction increased in the whole measurement temperature range (Fig.5 and

Fig.1 SEM micrographs of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites, (a) 0%Ni, (b) 10%Ni, (c) 15%Ni, (d) 20%Ni, (e) 25%Ni, (f) 35%Ni, and (g) 45%.

Fig.2 XRD patterns of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites.

Fig.3 Electrical resistivities of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites.

Fig.4 Ni volume fraction dependence of electrical resistivity of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites.

Fig.6). The Seebeck coefficient changed a gently trend and reached near that of Ni when the Ni volume fraction is 25% and above. It is supposed to relate to the increase of the carrier density with the increase of the volume fraction. For the composites with the same volume fraction of the added Ni powder, the Seebeck coefficient increased as the measurement temperature increased, however, the increase became less significant when the added volume fraction of Ni powder was above 22%. The power factor increased as measurement temperature increased as shown in Fig.7. When the volume fraction was 35%, the power factor reached the maximum value, $3.70 \times 10^{-4} \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-2}$ at 973 K.

Fig.5 Seebeck coefficient of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites.

Fig.7 Power factor of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites.

Fig.6 Ni volume fraction dependence of Seebeck coefficient of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites.

3.3 Carrier density and mobility of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites

The Hall coefficient of TiO_{2-x} (0%Ni) has a minus value, which is close with those of the reduced single or polycrystal TiO_{2-x} [13, 14] shown as in Fig.8. With the increase of Ni volume fraction, the absolute values of the Hall coefficient become small and approach that of Ni, $-0.61 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^3 \text{ C}^{-1}$ [15].

The carrier densities of the composites had a clear increase as the Ni volume fraction increased from about 10%, exceeded $1 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-3}$ like a metal when the volume fraction of the added Ni powder was more than 22% shown in Fig.9.

Meanwhile, the carrier mobility increased as the volume fraction of Ni increased as shown in Fig.10. It is consistent with the electrical behavior transition from semiconductor to metal due to the volume fraction of the added Ni powder as the electrical resistivity in Fig.3 and Fig.4. Further, it is found that the carrier concentration can be controlled in a large range by adding metal powder.

Fig.8 Hall coefficient of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites.

Here, we discuss the dependence of thermoelectric performance on the carrier concentration, referring to [16]. For metals or degenerate semiconductors, the Seebeck coefficient is given by equation 3.

$$S = \frac{8\pi^2 k_B^2}{3eh^2} m^* T \left(\frac{\pi}{3n}\right)^{2/3} \quad (3)$$

where n is the carrier concentration and m^* is the

effective mass of the carrier. The electrical

Fig.9 Carrier density of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites.

Fig.10 Carrier mobility of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites.

conductivity (σ)/resistivity (ρ) are related to n through the carrier mobility (μ) as follows.

$$1/\rho = \sigma = ne\mu \quad (4)$$

The compromise between large thermopower (Seebeck coefficient) and high electrical conductivity in thermoelectrics that must be struck to maximize the figure of merit ZT of a model material, which has the thermal conductivity from 0 to 10 Wm⁻¹K⁻¹ and the Seebeck coefficient from 0 to

500 μ VK⁻¹ with the electrical conductivity from 0 to 5000 Ω^{-1} cm⁻¹ as shown in Fig.11. The peak typically occurs at carrier concentration between 10²⁵ and 10²⁷ carriers per m³, which falls in between common metals and semiconductors, that is, concentrations found in heavily doped semiconductors or degenerate semiconductors.

However, composite technology frequently brought about some negative effects such as the increase of thermal conductivity. In our previous work, the thermal conductivity of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites was obtained by finite element method (FEM) and general effective medium equation (GEM) as shown in Fig.12.

The thermal conductivity of the composites increased with the increase of the Ni volume fraction. It must lead to the decrease of thermoelectric performance.

Fig.11 Dependence of thermoelectric properties on carrier concentration [16].

The thermal conductivity comes from two sources: electrons and holes transportation (κ_e) and phonons transportation (κ_l). Most of the electronic transportation (κ_e) is directly related to the electrical conductivity through the Wiedemann-Franz law as follows.

$$\kappa = \kappa_e + \kappa_l \quad (5)$$

and

$$\kappa_e = L\sigma T = ne\mu LT \quad (6)$$

where, L is the Lorenz factor, $2.4 \times 10^{-8} \text{ J}^2 \text{ K}^{-2} \text{ C}^{-2}$ for free electrons.

Therefore, reducing the lattice thermal conductivity is important to enhance the thermoelectric figure of

Fig. 12 Thermal conductivity of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites as a function of the Ni volume fraction [17].

merit. Here, we discuss the dependence of thermoelectric performance on the carrier concentration and thermal conductivity, referring to [16] again. An optimized ZT of 0.8 is shown at point A for a model thermoelectric material with a κ_l of $0.8 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ and κ_e that is a function of the carrier concentration shown in Fig.13. Reducing κ_l to $0.2 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ directly increase the ZT to point B. Additionally, lowering the thermal conductivity allows the carrier concentration to be reoptimized (reduced), leading to both a decrease in κ_e and a larger Seebeck coefficient. The reoptimized ZT is shown at point C. That is, it is very important for high performance thermoelectric materials to increase the power factor and to decrease the thermal conductivity by composite method.

In another work, high-performance bulk thermoelectrics was achieved through all-scale process including nano- and meso-scale [18]. Therefore, to improve the thermoelectric performance by composite method, the nano-composite and reactions at the interfaces should be introduced.

3.4 Band gap of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites

To obtain information about the energy band gap of the Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites and also understand the influence of adding Ni powder, the absorbance spectra of the composites were examined. The optical absorption edge was analyzed by Tauc equation [19, 20].

$$ahv = A(hv - E_g)^m \quad (7)$$

where A is the optical constant, a is the absorption coefficient, E_g is the optical band gap and m is 1/2 for direct transitions and 2 for indirect transitions. In this work, m was given with 2. Variation of $(ahv)^2$ with photon energy hv for the composites is shown in Fig.14. Band gap of TiO_{2-x} (0%Ni) is 2.35 eV, which is narrower than that (3.2 eV) of TiO₂ shown in Fig.15. Besides, band gap of the composites

Fig.13 Dependence of thermoelectric properties on carrier concentration and thermal conductivity [16].

Fig.14 $(ahv)^2 \sim hv$ plots of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites.

Fig.15 Band gap of Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites.

Fig.16 Schematic drawing of Burstein-moss effect.

becomes wider with volume fraction increase of the Ni. It is related with the increase of the carrier concentration as adding Ni powder shown in Fig.9. It was reported that band gap of TiO_{2-x} films became wider with increase of the carrier concentration [21]. With increase of carrier concentration, Burstein-moss shift [22] appears and it leads to band gap wider as shown in Fig.16.

4 Conclusions

The electrical resistivities of the Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites fabricated by SPS was decreased as the volume fraction of Ni powder increased. The electrical behavior transition of the Ni/TiO_{2-x} composites from semiconductor to metal can be controlled by adjusting the volume fraction of Ni powder. When the volume fraction was 35%, the power factor reached the maximum value, $3.70 \times 10^{-4} \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-2}$ at 973 K. The carrier concentration can be controlled in a large range by adding metal powder. Band gap of the composites becomes wider with volume fraction increase of the Ni.

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